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Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Adversity Quotient and Management Competence of School Heads in Region XI: A Convergent Design

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ABSTRACT

This study utilized mixed methods approach, specifically convergent design to determine the influence of organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient on the management competence of the school heads in Region XI. The participants of the study were the school heads in public secondary schools in Region XI. The data were gathered from the participants who were chosen purposively to participate both in the quantitative and qualitative phase of this study. Sets of adapted survey tools with a five-point Likert scale and an interview guide were used to extract data relative to the research questions. The mean, standard deviation, and linear regression were used as statistical tools. In the qualitative phase, thematic analysis in phenomenology was employed. Results showed that the status of organizational citizenship behavior, adversity quotient and management competence of the school heads were rated very high. Further, results showed that there was a significant relationship between organizational citizenship behavior, adversity quotient and management competence. In the qualitative phase of the study, four essential themes emerged as regards the lived experiences of school heads and these were: integral duties and responsibilities of school heads, leadership skills through commitment and dedication to service, a proactive leader, and leadership capabilities. Further, the nature of data integration revealed merging-converging.

INTRODUCTION

The recent challenges in the 21st century educational setting faced by the school heads brought 50 per cent of school heads' competence having difficulty in managing the schools. This is due to the shift of schools to digital technology, new learning modalities, student academic monitoring, new ways of communications, and new protocols in the operations of schools (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development-OECD, 2019). In addition, school leaders were confused and burdened of unexpected shift to a new educational management set-up due to challenges in the field of education. Thus, management competence among school heads were challenged (Brackett & Cipriano, 2020; Educational Institute of Scotland, 2020). Further, the abrupt shift in new educational paradigm led the school leaders being confronted on how their existing school management competence would fit in the context of their school situation, in order to address the needs of school during adversities (Nannyonjo *et al.*, 2021).

Globally, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Education- Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (UNICEF, 2020), state that adversities brought by the on-going health crisis made school heads having difficulties in managing schools since the existing skills are not totally fit to their context. Particularly, school heads thrive on managing the human resource particularly the safety and welfare of the teachers and students' health, the insufficient and late allocation of financial resources due to budget re-alignment and reductions, managing poor communications to teachers,

parents and learners, the implementation crisis response planning, and maintaining organizational continuity are among issue on management (Kruse *et al.*, 2020; Educational Institute of Scotland 2021).

In addition, at the end of March 2020, more than 5,000 school administrators in the United States expressed apprehensions which affected their teaching and school management skills. Specifically managing new methods of living and working while also managing their own concerns and doubts which most of them has not attended a training or no skills in dealing such problem brought by health crises (Brackett & Cipriano 2020). Likewise, school heads had suffered capability to separate their workdays from their personal lives and spent several hours late at night and on weekends attempting to run their schools and care for the school community. Similarly, in many situations, school heads' responsibilities stretched beyond strictly academic work, prioritizing fundamental requirements before addressing instructional problems. It resulted to the lesser priority of other aspects of school management, thus, the school heads having problem on balancing the equal important aspects in managing school (Kaul *et al.*, 2021).

In the Philippines, as of 2020, there are 748 out of 14,435 private basic educational institutions suspended operations which affected 3,233 teachers and 40,345 learners (CNN Philippines, 2020). This situation in private schools, challenged the competence of school heads to encourage their learners to continue to study in their institution (Pitagan, 2020). Meanwhile, the sudden transfer of learners from the private schools to public

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schools triggers more management problems on how to address the financial and human resources that are limited and on the academic and non-academic needs of the learners (Chi & Cuyco, 2021).

Further, school heads who are not technology-savvy or competent had their difficulty on tasks which involve technological competence. This is prevalent recently since there are only 95,156 or 11 per cent of the total teaching force of 847,467 including school heads had been trained (DEPED Commons, 2020). Furthermore, there is a need for a national learning platform and a centralized module creation to ensure quality and standards of the modules which become the concern of the school heads on how to manage instructions to ensure the quality of instructional materials (Pitagan, 2021).

Banking on the above-mentioned premises, this study was conceptualized to determine the influence of organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient on their management competence. There had been several studies describing only the relationship of organizational citizenship behavior with other variable, these studies were bivariate in nature (Hasanuddin, 2020; Yao & Mingchua, 2010; Luthans, 2011; Soumendu & Arup, 2007; Boerner *et al.* (2007) and Chiang & Tsung, 2012). Other studies focused also on management competence in the corporate world though these were in quantitative in nature (Suryadi & Santoso, 2017; Juwita, 2020; Bautista, 2015; and Chunin *et al.*, 2018). What made this study novel was the utilization of mixed methods design, having the school heads in the local region as the respondents. Evidently, most of the studies had only an individual association between variables, whereas in the present study had an association between organizational citizenship behavior, adversity quotient and management competence among school heads.

Furthermore, the study of Hasanuddin (2020) stated that organizational citizenship behavior has a positive effect on the performance. In addition, the study also revealed that 70 percent of the participants of the study shows that the OCB explains the performance and competence towards the responsibilities of the participants on their organization. This also supported the study of Yao & Mingchuan (2010) and Amalia *et al.* (2021) were the organizational citizenship behavior explained 65 percent of individual competence in performing the job, thus, OCB had a positive effect on school heads performance which explain that the organizational citizenship behavior of individual, group and organizational competence in performing such job roles in an organization are positively related (Soumendu & Arup, 2007; Boerner *et al.* (2007); Chiang (2012); Luthans (2011).

Added on, the role of adversity quotient is interrelated on the ability or competence and achievement of a person which is 66.67 percent (Suryadi & Santoso, 2017), while with knowledge and understanding is 27.78 percent and with positive attitude is 5.56 percent, based on systematic review and meta-analysis (Juwita, 2020). Further, in the study of Bautista (2015), it was revealed that 66 percent

of the teachers involved of the study has high adversity quotient with good competence and performance. Moreover, it supported the study of Chunin *et al.* (2018) which also revealed that majority of the school leaders successfully able to perform well due to their high adversity quotient.

Moreover, the study determined the influence of organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient toward management competence of the school heads in Region XI. Specifically, it sought answers to the following research questions:

1. What are the levels of organizational citizenship behavior, adversity quotient and management competence of school heads?
2. Do organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient significantly influence management competence of school heads?
3. What are the lived experiences of the school heads with regard to their management competence?
4. How do these experiences shape the beliefs, attitude, and commitment of the school heads?
5. How do the qualitative data corroborate with the quantitative findings?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). The organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) refers to any good and productive acts and behaviors that are not part of the formal job description of an individual. It is anything that persons do out of the goodness of their hearts to help their coworkers and the organization (Verlinden, 2021). As emphasized by Somech & Drach-Zahavy (2004), if a person exhibits OCB, it may make a good impression on superiors, which might lead to employment advantages such as greater salary or a promotion (Organ, 2016). OCB is influenced by both preconceptions and adaptability, expected rewards from this kind of behavior. Further, the categories of organizational Citizenship behavior linked primary behaviors beneficial to the outcomes for organizations namely, altruism, courtesy, sportsmanship, conscientiousness, and civic virtue.

Altruism

Altruism is the conduct of any individual to promote the wellbeing of others at their own expense, even at the risk of their own life. It is seen as selfless action in which no reward is expected in return (Smith *et al.*, 2006).

Courtesy

Courtesy encompasses actions to prevent difficulties and take the required steps to mitigate the problem's future consequences. In other words, when a person feels depressed and disappointed about their professional progress, courtesy implies he or she supports others (Muthuraman & Al-Haziizi, 2017).

Conscientiousness

This concept is characterized as voluntary actions

displayed by organization members that go above the minimal duties in specific areas of the organization's internal order, such as attendance, timeliness, and resource protection (Yen & Neihoff, 2004).

Civic Virtue

Civic virtue is described that the employees are responsibly involved and support the strategies, voluntarily becoming committees or attending a function organized by the organization (Sharma & Jain, 2014).

Sportsmanship

This concept refers a persons' actions when dealing with unexpected inconveniences in the organization without complaint and yet still doing their best (Ehtiyar *et al.*, 2010).

Adversity Quotient (AQ)

The Adversity Quotient (AQ) by Stoltz (2001) explained that it is primarily responsible for one's success in life. In addition, AQ is a complementary conceptual framework for understanding and enhancing all facets of success, as well as a scientifically grounded tool to measure how one responds to adversity and how effectively a someone can tolerate and overcome hardship (Balita, 2021). Similarly, AQ is a measure of a person's ability to think about, control, steer, and accept life's obstacles. In other words, it is the science of human resilience, people who apply it effectively perform at their best in the face of adversity and the obstacles that we encounter every day, and they not only learn from these difficulties, but they also respond to them more effectively and quickly (Nikam & Uplane, 2013).

Control

This refers to the ability of individual to positively influence a situation and be able to control the response to the situation. Those with higher AQs perceived they have significantly more control and influence in adverse situations than do those with lower AQs (Stoltz, 2001).

Ownership

This dimension refers to the individual's ability to place feelings and dare to bear the consequences of the situation resulted to make developments to the problems that occur (Chadha, 2021).

Reach

This dimension refers under control and limiting the reach of adversity is essential for efficient and effective problem solving (Aquino, 2013).

Endurance

This dimension refers to the ability of individuals to perceive difficulties, and strength in dealing with these difficulties by creating ideas in problem solving so that the hardness of heart and courage in solving problems can be realized (Runtu *et al.*, 2019).

School Management Competence

The success of the organization in accordance with its defined goals is referred to as management. It covers results that have been attained or acquired because of individual competence and group contributions to the attainment of organizational goals (Kapur, 2020).

School Leadership

In this category, individuals with leadership skills have characteristics and talents that enable them to monitor procedures, drive projects, and steer their people toward achieving their mission, vision, goals and objectives (McLaughlin, 2014).

Instructional Leadership

In this category, the instructional leadership purpose is centered on facilitating deeper student learning, professional inquiry, trusting relationships, and finding evidence in action characterizes (Timperley, 2011). This includes creating a student-centered learning climate by setting high social and academic expectations and creating environment according to the needs of the learners (Le Fevre *et al.*, 2020; Mungasia, J. A., Ouda, J. B., & Otieno, K. 2022).

Resource Management and Allocation

This category focuses on the practice of planning, scheduling, and allocating people, money, and technology to a project or program and this is also known as the school management and operations which includes implementation of the annual plans, strategic plans as well as the fiscal management and the use of technology in management operations (Townsend, 2021).

Human Resource Management

This aspect of school management is concerned with the organization's teachers and non-teaching staff (The Balance Careers, 2021).

Program Monitoring and Reporting

In this category it involves the communication of the current standing of a certain program or projects. In addition, this aspect of school management is critical to measure and evaluate program effectiveness, it's equally critical to effectively communicate with others about the results (Malone *et al.*, 2014).

Professional Development Practices

This aspect of school management encompasses a wide range of educational opportunities relating to the teachers by applying new information through the participation in professional development as well as enhancement of the abilities that will help them perform better on the job (Antley, 2021).

Community Collaboration

In this aspect of school management, it focuses on the collaboration with other members of the community for the greater good (Queensland Department of Education, 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design. This study utilized the mixed methods research particularly convergent design. In this method, the researcher gathered two types of data – quantitative and qualitative data at about the same time and then combines the data into the overall findings’ that resulted to a solid framework for analyzing outcomes and interpretation (Creswell & Plano-Clark, 2011; Mason, 2006). Convergent design was introduced by Creswell (2013) in which the quantitative and qualitative strands of the research are performed independently, and their results are brought together in the overall interpretation. This design was used to check, cross-validate, and verify results.

Locale

This study was conducted in Region XI or also known as Davao Region. Davao Region is located at Southeastern part of Mindanao Island in Southern part of the Philippines.

Participants

In the quantitative phase, there were 500 teachers from the secondary and integrated schools in Region XI participated in this study for the quantitative survey. They were chosen through purposive sampling technique. The researcher had chosen the teachers who were assigned, designated, or appointed as teachers for at least one year in the current school since they had enough experience with their school heads. In the qualitative aspect, a total of 19 participants were involved in the study, 12 participants confirmed and participated in the in-depth interview (IDI) and another seven participants confirmed and participated in the focus group discussions (FGD). For the IDI and FGD, the following criteria were observed: the school heads are permanent with plantilla position as school head or teacher-in-charge or head teacher, and is designated in the current school for at least one year.

Research Instruments

In the quantitative phase, survey questionnaires were utilized to gather data from the participants. For the measurement instrument of the organizational citizenship behavior of the school heads, the Organizational Citizenship Behavior Questionnaire was utilized. The questionnaire is adapted from Podsakoff *et al.* (2000). Meanwhile, the school heads adversity quotient was measured through the Adversity Quotient Profile (AQP) Stoltz (1997). Lastly, for the level of school heads’ management competence, the instrument utilized was the National Competency-Based Standards for School Heads (NCBSSH) developed and validated through the AusAID-funded project STRIVE (Strengthening the Implementation of Basic Education in Selected Provinces in the Visayas), in coordination with the Educational Development Project Implementing Task Force (DepEd No. 32, s. 2010). In the qualitative phase, there was a researcher-made interview guide utilized in the conduct of the in-depth interview and focus group

discussion which is composed of open-ended questions. The guide questions were validated by the five experts. The objective of this qualitative instrument was to explore the participants’ lived experiences regarding their management competence as school managers.

Data Collection and Analysis

During the conduct of the study in quantitative phase, the researcher sought consent from the respondents, and they were informed on the entire process of data collection and made them to understand the different dimensions of ethical consideration during the data gathering. Before the administration of survey questionnaire, the informed consent form was given to the participants and returned to the researcher as evidence of allowing the researcher to conduct the study. In the qualitative phase of the study, the researcher conducted IDI and FGD to further strengthen the study. After obtaining the necessary approval to conduct the study, an appointment was set by the researcher. Meanwhile, before the conduct of the study in qualitative phase, the purpose of the study was explained and made understood to the participants. Further, during the conduct of the IDI, the interview was done via online platforms in a one-on-one interview. In analyzing the data in the quantitative strand, the researcher used the following statistical treatments to analyze and interpret the data; mean, standard deviation, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and Regression Analysis. For the qualitative phase, a step-by-step process was applied based from Collaizzi’s (1978) descriptive phenomenological method. The method is rigorous and robust that the researchers used to find, understand, describe and depict the experiences of the participants as they experience them, as well as reveal emergent themes and their interwoven relationships (Wirihana *et al.*, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Table 1 presents the results of the organizational citizenship behavior of school heads. It has an over-all mean rating of 4.42, described as very high. It means that the organizational citizenship behaviors of school heads are always evident. This shows that school heads are characterized with good and productive acts and behaviors that are not part of the formal job description of an individual. In addition, the overall standard deviation is .68 which is less than one denoting that the respondents have ratings that are practically almost the same.

Altruism

In particular, the result of the category of altruism OCB of the school heads is very high indicating that it is always evident with a category mean rating of 4.33.

Courtesy

Meanwhile, the result of the category of courtesy OCB of the school heads is also very high indicating that it is

always evident with a category mean of 4.41.

Conscientiousness

In addition, the result of the category of conscientiousness OCB of the school heads is very high indicating that it is always evident with a category mean rating of 4.46.

Civic Virtue

Similarly, the result of the category of civic virtue OCB of the school heads is also very high indicating that it is always evident with a category mean of 4.45.

Sportsmanship

Similarly, the result of the category of sportsmanship OCB of the school heads is also very high indicating that it is always evident with a category mean of 4.44. This finding supports the study of Halbesleben & Bellairs

(2016), which state that OCBs seek to enhance present workplace situations by raising issues, taking the initiative in making changes, or improving existing procedures or relationships in the organization. In addition, the study of Verlinden (2021) also explained that school heads who exhibits OCB may make a good impression with the organization performance and also characterized by a person who had a goodness of their hearts to help their coworkers and the organization.

Furthermore, Organ *et al.* (2016) also discussed that since OCB influences the organizational, social, and psychological environment of a person which acts as the crucial catalyst for task activities and processes, thus, it improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the person. Moreover, OCB can boost the performance of an individual as well as the organization (Udin & Yuniawan, 2020).

Table 1: Status of Organizational Citizenship Behavior of School Heads

Category	Mean	SD	Description
Altruism	4.33	.77	Very High
Courtesy	4.41	.77	Very High
Conscientiousness	4.46	.68	Very High
Civic Virtue	4.45	.69	Very High
Sportsmanship	4.42	.72	Very High
Overall Mean	4.42	.68	Very High

Status of Adversity Quotient of School Heads

Table 2 presents the results of the adversity quotient of school heads. It has an over-all mean of 4.39, described as very high. It means that the adversity quotient of school heads is always manifested. Further, the result also mean that school heads posit high responds to adversity and how the school heads effectively tolerate and overcome adversities. In addition, the overall standard deviation is .69 which is less than one denoting that the respondents have ratings that are practically almost the same.

Control

The result of the category of control AQ of the school heads is very high indicating that it is always manifested with a category mean of 4.37.

Ownership

The result of the category of ownership AQ of the school heads is very high indicating that it is always manifested with a category mean of 4.42.

Reach

The result of the category of reach AQ of the school heads is very high indicating that it is always manifested with a category mean of 4.38. It is noted that the mean rating of the items are ranges from 4.35 to 4.41.

Endurance

The result of the category of endurance AQ of the school heads is very high indicating that it is always manifested with a category mean of 4.39. It is noted that the mean rating of the items are ranges from 4.38 to 4.40. The result demonstrates that the adversity quotient

of school heads is always manifested by their capacity to consider, control, steer, and accept work-related obstacles and challenges. It also suggests that this factor evaluates how a person reacts to and handles both minor inconveniences and significant setbacks whether in life or in an organization. Further, the finding corroborates with the research conducted by Fadhila *et al.* (2020) which claims that a person's ability to think about, manage, influence, and accept life's challenges determines how individuals adapt to it and handle both minor inconveniences and significant failures in life. This signifies that the probability that school heads will be able to deal with different challenges they may face in their day-to-day job as school heads increases with the amount of adversity quotient among them. In support, the finding confirms the statement of Ablaña *et al.* (2016) which explicated that the existence of a person's personal problems, including the stress that accompanies of work, or the frustration of someone meeting his coworkers every day and the number of unexpected events is a test of resilience to overcome and continue life, thus adversity quotient is a tool to face and succeed from it. In the study it was manifested among the school heads. Thus, the adversity quotient is a complementary conceptual framework for understanding and increasing all aspects of achievement as well as a scientifically based technique to assess how well school leaders can endure and overcome adversity (Balita, 2021).

Status of Management Competence of School Heads

Table 3 presents the results of the management competence of school heads. It has an over-all mean of 4.38, described as very high. It means that the management

Table 2: Status of Organizational Citizenship Behavior of School Heads

Category	Mean	SD	Description
Control	4.37	.71	Very High
Ownership	4.42	.70	Very High
Reach	4.38	.71	Very High
Endurance	4.39	.75	Very High
Sportsmanship	4.42	.72	Very High
Overall Mean	4.39	.69	Very High

competence of school heads is always demonstrated. Further, the result also reflects how competent the school heads in different aspects of management competence. In addition, the overall standard deviation is .62 which is less than one denoting that the respondents have ratings that are practically almost the same.

School Leadership

For this category, it was subdivided into six sub-categories namely Developing and Communicating Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO), Data-Based Strategic Planning, Problem Solving, Building High Performance Teams, Coordinating with Others and Leading and Managing Change. This category has a mean rating of 4.35 which means that the school heads are always demonstrated a very high management competence.

Instructional Leadership

Under this category, it consists of four sub- categories namely, assessment for learning, developing programs and or adopting existing programs, implementing programs for instructional improvement and instructional supervision. This category has a mean rating of 4.32 which means that the school heads are always demonstrated a very high management competence on instructional leadership.

Creating a Student-centered Learning Climate

Meanwhile this category composed of two sub- categories namely, setting high social and academic expectations and creating school environment focused on the needs of the learner. This category has a mean rating of 4.41 which means that the school heads always demonstrated a very high management competence on creating a student-centered learning climate.

Human Resource Management and Professional Development

Further, this category composed of three sub- categories namely, creating a professional learning community, recruitment and hiring and managing performance of teachers and staff. This category has a mean rating of 4.35 which means that the school heads always demonstrated a very high management competence on dealing their human resource management and professional development.

Parent Involvement and Community Partnership

This category composed of two sub-categories namely parental involvement and external community partnership. The overall mean of this sub-category is 4.39

which is interpreted as very high. This means that parent involvement and community partnership category under the management competence of school heads are always demonstrated in their day-to-day school management.

School Management and Daily Operations

This category composed of three sub-categories managing school operation, fiscal management, and the use of technology in the management of operations. The overall mean of this sub-category is 4.36 which is interpreted as very high. This means that school management and daily operations category under the management competence of school heads are always demonstrated.

Personal and Professional Attributes and Interpersonal Effectiveness

For this category it composed of four sub- categories namely, professionalism, communication, interpersonal sensitivity and fairness, honesty, and integrity. The overall mean rating of personal and professional attributes and interpersonal effectiveness of school heads is 4.43 which is also interpreted as very high. This means that the personal and professional attributes and interpersonal effectiveness category of management competence of school heads are always demonstrated.

The results are consistent with the research of Valamis (2020) which also discussed how an individual’s ability to manage their schoolwork can assist them in identifying the skills required for job success, assessing their current skill set to identify any gaps, and providing the necessary training to help them fill those gaps. Thus, school heads competence will also give them assurance that they will be more successful in dealing their responsibilities in their school. Further, school heads competence will also give them realization to become more competent by improving their skills in school management. The finding also confirms the study of Armstrong (2011) which explained that having a deeper comprehension of the skills required for an organization to develop and progress. The same goes for having high competency, which Rothwell *et al.* (2015) said may assist establish a competent, dedicated leadership team that will engage people and transform them into long-term assets.

Additionally, in recent years, competence in school administration has been defined as a purposeful impact on interactions and activities based on a distinct sense of direction (Bush & Glover, 2003; Pont *et al.*, 2008; Louis *et al.*, 2010). The key elements of school administration that school administrators must grasp in order to be effective leaders have been the subject of several studies. Effective

school leadership has given rise to a variety of theories over time. The importance of managerial competency has also been highlighted in research (Bush & Glover, 2003; Mulford, 2008). This kind of view is associated with the notion that schools are professional groups (Spillane & Kenney, 2012).

Moreover, Day *et al.* (2009 & 2010) had updated the commonly cited essential leadership techniques that serve as the basis for management competency in direction-setting, organizational restructuring, employee

development, and managing teaching and learning. Additionally, effective school leaders are those who redesign leadership roles and responsibilities, restructure parts of the organization, and change the environment for teaching and learning in order to raise standards, build trust, improve curriculum, enhance teacher effectiveness, enhance teaching and learning quality, encourage internal cooperation, forge strong ties outside of the school community, and establish their values and vision (Leithwood *et al.*, 2006)

Table 3: Status of Management Competence of School Heads

	Mean	SD	Description
School Leadership	4.35	.65	Very High
Instructional Leadership	4.32	.67	Very High
Creating a Student-Centered Learning Climate	4.41	.65	Very High
HR Management and Professional Development	4.35	.68	Very High
Parent Involvement and Community Partnership	4.39	.69	Very High
School Management and Daily Operations	4.36	.66	Very High
Personal and Professional Attributes and Interpersonal Effectiveness	4.43	.67	Very High
Overall Mean	4.38	.62	Very High

Significance of the Influence of Organizational Citizenship Behaviors and Adversity Quotient on Management Competence of School Heads

Table 4 shows the significance of the influence of organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient on the management competence of school heads. The finding shows that the organizational citizenship behavior has significant influence on management competence of school heads as evidenced by a p-value of .000 and a positive standardized beta value of .480.

This indicates that for every unit increase in the organizational citizenship behaviors of school heads, there is a corresponding .480 increase in the management competence of school heads. Likewise, the results

shows that the adversity quotient of school heads has a p- value of less than .000 and a positive standardized beta value of .427. This indicates that for every unit increase in the adversity quotient of school heads, there is a corresponding .427 increase in the management competence of school heads.

Furthermore, the model shows 79 percent of the school performance as revealed in the R-squared value of .796 is explained by school heads’ organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient. This suggests that 21 percent of the variance of school heads’ management competence can be attributed to other factors aside from organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient of the school heads.

Table 4: Significance of the Influence of Organizational Citizenship Behaviors and Adversity Quotient on Management Competence of School Heads

	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	p-value	Interpretation
OCB	.480	8.463	.000	Significant
ACQ	.427	7.536	.000	Significant

R = .892 R Square = .796 F = 970.592 p value = .000

Lived Experiences of School Heads on Management Competence

On the lived experiences of school heads as regards their management competence, four essential themes had emerged, integral duties and responsibilities of school heads, leadership skills through commitment to service, proactive leader and leadership capabilities.

Integral Duties and Responsibilities of School Heads

The results disclosed that being a school head has an integral duties and responsibilities that must be fulfilled. This theme suggests that they had to attend several duties and responsibilities such as providing the effective instructional and developmental measures through supervising teachers, monitoring curricular programs to ensure high standard quality education. School heads also

added that being a school head their main duty is being responsible in over-all smooth school operations and to carry out the educational programs even despite of the difficulties they encountered. This theme confirms the propositions of Bandura’s Social Career Cognitive Theory where people with strong self-efficacy are more likely to become interested in or choose to pursue and competent in their field if they also have the requisite abilities and environmental supports (Gushue & dan Whitson, 2006; Nauta, 2004).

Leadership Skills and Commitment to Service

As shared by the school heads, they agreed that being a school head should have the leadership skills and commitment to service. This means that as school head they are accountable on their school. They need to demonstrate support towards school programs, activities

and projects that will help the learners. Thus, they also need to observe teachers and give them technical assistance as much as possible to address the needs of the learners and provide the needs of students, teachers and the school. This validates the study conducted by McLaughlin (2014) which stressed that it is always the responsibility of school heads to oversee operations, oversee projects, and direct their teachers toward accomplishing school goals. The theme also supports the study of Rothwell (2015) which stated that having a better knowledge and competence as the head of a school will enable the organization to develop and prosper in the future.

A Proactive Leader

As shared by the school heads, it was generated that being a school head should be a proactive leader. Being proactive means, they have tolerance against pressures and stresses by and had an appropriate values and virtues, facing the problems either big or small and being able to adapt and attuned to the walk of time. This validates the result of the study of Manzon (2021) and Hong (2020) which they found that a school leaders adversity quotient was a good indicator of their competency. This also conforms the study of Muthuraman & Al-Haziati (2017) which revealed that having a high level of courtesy made school heads avoid problems and take the necessary actions to lessen the problem's long-term effects.

Leadership Capabilities

Lastly, school heads had shared that school head must be a goal oriented by looking forward for the welfare of the students and teachers, by investing in school development and its personnel. This can be attributed to school leadership, instructional and human resource management competence of the school heads. This is consistent with the research of Usman (2016) which found out that fostering a positive learning environment result in students and teachers having higher expectations for themselves and for one another. This can be also linked to the management of human resources and the teachers ongoing professional development. Since it deals with the system of management observations and evaluations focusing on such areas as organizing and delivering instruction, managing instructional resources, monitoring, and assessing progress, and accommodating diverse learning styles, human resources are a crucial part of the school management aspect (Sherman, 2002).

Role of Experiences in Shaping the Belief, Attitude, Commitment of School Heads

Guiding Principles of Effective Educational Landscape

Being a school head must uphold guiding principles of effective educational landscape. This means as school head they believed that exemplary teaching and good leadership is necessary in leading the school. They further shared that teaching is a noble profession and education is not only contained within the four corners of classroom. In addition, as a school head they need to uphold the

highest standards of education and not to settle for less. The theme emerged substantiates the study of Podsakoff *et al.* (2000) in which they discussed that civic virtue has a role to be effective leader in educational landscape. As they explained that school heads are primarily involved in achieving the total organizational commitment and concerned with the image and reputation of the school organization. In connection, this theme also confirms the study of Somech & Drach-Zahavy (2004) which also highlighted how the school heads altruistic OCB acted as an incentive for them to view their position as a vocation rather than merely a career. They pledged to sustain the greatest level of education, one that goes beyond the four walls of the classroom, as they spoke.

Holistic Characteristics of a School Leader

School heads shared that their attitude in managing school was shaped by the experiences that they had endured. Several of them shared the as a school head there is a need to possess favorable attitude by being mindful of self-development maintaining a wholesome outlook in the workplace. They also believed that experiences are the best teacher, especially in facing challenges positively and maintaining good relationship with others. The generated theme validates the studies of Muthuraman & Al-Haziati (2017) where they highlighted the concept of courtesy. In the concept of courtesy, the school leaders promote an atmosphere where all teachers participate in decision-making process and also promote open communication. This will open good dialogue and good working atmosphere among stakeholders of the school. The theme that emerged strengthens the Resiliency Theory, with school heads developed their dispositions through their experiences (Stoltz, 2001). This idea holds that when a person encounters hardship, tragedy, or frustration in life, these things aid in their recovery and enable them to accomplish the organizational goal by strengthening their capacity to complete the duties they have set for themselves.

Sustainable and Quality Education

As the school heads shared during the interview, the quality learning and teaching goals is important in performing the expected deliverables in teaching. They also added the as school heads must do the tasks and responsibilities in school properly. In addition, the school heads also revealed that school heads must be laden with values, like being a person of integrity, a person who is God as the center of plans, being kind, respect and honest as the best ingredient of leadership. This can be trace with the professional development among school heads. This theme generated supports the Code of Ethics of Professional School Heads/ Teachers under Republic Act 7836 (Res. 435 s. 1998) where such characteristics of personal and professional such as respect, honesty, devotion, patriotism, and genuine care for others. In addition, school leaders maintain pleasant and harmonious personal official relationships with superiors,

colleagues, subordinates, students, parents, and other stakeholders (DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2010). The claim of the school heads corroborates with the study of Khalil (2004) which stated that OCB is has its role towards the delivery of quality learning and teaching goals. The theme also conforms with the study of Bukhari *et al.* (2009) that the conscientiousness where the school heads have this virtue not only settle for good, but they serve the school beyond the minimal duties and responsibilities stated in their job description thus they had a passion to the school vision.

Data Integration of Salient Qualitative and Quantitative Findings

On the focal point organizational citizenship behavior, the quantitative results corroborate with qualitative findings. All items are having a merging converging quantitative and qualitative data. For altruism, the merging-converging of data was in consonance with the study of Smith *et al.* (2006) which stated that altruism makes the school heads become selfless in doing their duties and responsibilities. Meanwhile, the item on courtesy, the merging-converging of data corroborates with the study by Muthuraman & Al-Haziati (2017) and Podsakoff *et al.* (2000) which stated that having a very high level of courtesy, this means that school heads are promoting a school environment that has a culture of politeness, cooperation, and compassion. On the one hand, the item on conscientiousness, the merging-converging of data confirms the research of Yen and Neihoff (2004) in which they highlighted that volunteer acts above and above the call of duty in particular areas of school administration were a hallmark of school leaders. The item on civic virtue, the merging-converging of data strengthens the study of Jacqueline *et al.* (2004) which explained that civic virtue can be attributed to the school head who has keeping on track the updates of the school. Lastly, the item on sportsmanship, the merging-converging of data was in consonance with the study of Podsakoff *et al.* (2000) which explained that sportsmanship among school heads can improve workgroup morale while lowering attrition rates.

On the focal point adversity quotient, the quantitative results corroborate with qualitative findings. It was observed that all categories under adversity quotient has a merging-converging of data was formed.

The item on control, the merging-converging of data was in congruence with the study of Stoltz (2000) which stated that having a very high level of control the school heads have an ability of to positively influence a situation and be able to control the response to the situation. The item on ownership, the merging-converging of data substantiates the study of Chadha (2021) in which the accountability is the backbone of action. Thus, school heads with higher ownership hold themselves accountable for dealing with situations regardless of their cause. Another item is on reach, the merging-converging of data was in consonance with the study of by Viswanat (2020) which found that people with higher AQ levels keep their setbacks and

problems in check and prevent them from invading more positive aspects of their job and personal life. Lastly, the item on endurance, the merging-converging of data is in consonance with the study of Runtu *et al.* (2019), that those school heads with higher endurance can see past in the most undermorable difficulties and maintain hope and optimism.

On the focal point management competence, the quantitative results corroborate with qualitative findings. It can be observed that all categories under management competence has a merging-converging data.

The item on school leadership, the merging-converging of data confirms the research of McLaughlin (2014) which that found that a school leader's responsibility is to make defensible decisions about the vision and objectives of their organization. The second the item on instructional leadership, the merging-converging of data conforms with the statements found that showed instructional leadership aspires to establish a secure learning environment and efficient solutions for students' needs (Cotton, 2000). The third is the item on creating a student-centered learning climate, the merging-converging of data supports the study of Usman (2016) which stated that school heads must promote a good school learning that will result to an effective teaching and learning. The fourth is the item on human resource management and professional development, the merging-converging of data validates the study of Antley (2021) which stated that by applying new trends in teaching through the participation in professional development as well as enhancement of the abilities that will help them perform the teachers better. The fifth is the item on parent involvement and community partnership, the merging-converging data supports the study done in Queensland Department of Education (2019) which revealed that school heads with good collaboration skills with the community allows their schools to have a deeper grasp of their larger community and to form strong bonds within their own community. The sixth is the item on school management and daily operations, the merging-converging data validates the study of Malone *et al.* (2014) which explained that part of the school management and daily operation is the consistent monitoring of the programs of the school. Lastly, the item on personal and professional attributes and interpersonal effectiveness, the merging-converging of data strengthens the claims of McLaughlin (2014) which stated that school leadership involves not only on the technical aspects of leadership in school, but it also included the competence of the school heads to have good relationship, emotionally with the teachers.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of the study: The organizational citizenship behavior of the school heads was rated very high. This implies that the altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, civic virtue, and sportsmanship were always evident among school heads. Hence, the school heads in Region

XI demonstrated a voluntary behavior commitment to their schools beyond their duties and responsibilities. Meanwhile the adversity quotient ability of the school heads was also rated very high. This result implies that adversity quotient on control, ownership, reach, and endurance are always manifested. Findings revealed that school heads had a very high ability to think about, control, steer, and accept the obstacles, challenges encountered and evaluate with little annoyances setbacks in the workplace. In addition, the management competence of the school heads was also rated very high. This result implies that the management competence on school leadership, instructional leadership, in creating a student-centered learning climate, HR Management and professional development, parent involvement and community partnership, school management and daily operations are the personal and professional attributes which are relevant to the interpersonal effectiveness of the school heads in the different aspects of school management.

The influence of organizational citizenship behavior and the adversity quotient had a significant influence on the management competence of the school heads. This indicates as the organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient increases, there is also a corresponding increase of the school heads' management competence. These results would give implication that the organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient are contributory characteristics on how well the management competence of the school heads would be in their respective school organization.

Further, four essential themes emerged from the lived experiences of the participants. These themes were integral duties and responsibilities of school heads, leadership skills and commitment to service, a proactive leader and leadership capabilities. Likewise, the themes emerged regarding the role of experiences which shaped their beliefs and attitudes towards the school management were guiding principles of effective educational landscape, wholesome characteristics of a school leader and sustainable and quality education are the attitudes and commitment of the school heads.

Additionally, when the quantitative results were merged with qualitative results, a merging-converging nature was found to exist in organizational citizenship behavior, adversity quotient and management competence of the school heads.

The following recommendations were presented based on the findings of the study:

1. Since the organizational citizenship behavior revealed a very-high level, to sustain this ability shown by the school heads, the schools division superintendent, public schools district supervisors and human resource officers may conduct of seminars and trainings in enhancing the school heads' skills in the promotion of supportive, positive relationships and rapport within the workplace.

2. Since the adversity quotient revealed a very high level, to sustain this ability shown by the school heads, the

school division offices, public schools district supervisors and senior educational program specialists may conduct a capacity building particularly life coaching to promote productivity which may help school heads to be more resilient, persistent, adaptable, and high endurance in taking challenges.

3. Since the management competence of the school heads is very high, to sustain this ability shown by the school heads, the regional chief of the human resource division and the regional director may revisit the Philippine Professional Standards for school heads in the context of the regional level and may be endorsed to the central office for their assessment and enhancement of school heads standards in managing schools.

4. Since the result of the linear regression analysis revealed that organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient predicted the management competence of school heads in Region XI, future researchers may explore on other factors that may affect the management competence of the school heads aside form organizational citizenship behavior and adversity quotient.

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